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CONSCIOUS VERSUS UNCONSCIOUS SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE DECISION-MAKING

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the perspectives of designers in terms of their perception of the relationship between CSR and design. A series of in-depth interviews with practicing designers were the primary method of data gathering. Based on our findings, as well as our literature review, this research classifies conscious and unconscious design decision-making in terms of the social and environmental issues, within a range of regulated to non-regulated issues by the company. The article concludes by offering providing a framework to evaluate where CSR decisions are being made, and how conscious and unconscious socially responsible design decisions affect CSR particularly in the new product development process, with special reference to the electronics industry in South Korea.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility(CSR), socially responsible design(SRD), new product development (NPD).

1. INTRODUCTION

Although a precise definition remains elusive, the term corporate social responsibility (CSR) is heard more and more often in business circles. CSR originally implied giving back to society in a philanthropic sense. It is now increasingly used in a strategic sense, to refer to a business practice that allows for the integration of social and environmental considerations with a firm's business operations through the effective alignment of philanthropic contributions with business goals and strategies (Drucker, 1984; Freeman and Gillbert, 1998; European Commission, 2002; Porter and Kramer, 2002; Stead and Stead, 2004). Moreover, this is done in a manner that respects the legitimate goals and demands of all stakeholders (Carroll, 1979; Clarkson 1995; Waddock et al. 2002; Business for Social Responsibility, 2003; and Heslin and Ochoa, 2008). For this reason,

many argue that addressing CSR is not just a task for an organization's public relations department; rather, if it is to be a holistic and strategic approach, it must permeate every facet of the company, from marketing to finance, production, and design(Freeman and Gilbert, 1998; Porter and Kramer, 2006; Carroll and Buchholtz, 2008; Green, 2010). It follows that if designers and design managers wish to continue to play a role in corporate strategy development, they must integrate CSR considerations into the key results they produce (Thackara, 2009; Hands, 2009).

In the design field since the 1970s there have been continuous attempts by designers to be motivated and interested in enhancing the environmental and social impact of the products they create (e.g. Papanek, 1971 and1983; and Whiteley, 1993). However, within the industrial context, this forward looking philosophy is not adequately applied in the new product development process. In recent years, along with the ever-strengthening regulations around the world, large industry's commitment to integrating environmental and social issues into product development is gradually increasing. A growing number of researchers since the 1980s have built on Papanek (1971)'s ideas that socially responsible design approaches can have a central and distinct role in the view of market-based design (Senge, 2008). In particular, the 'market model' and 'social model' of design management are no longer considered to be in opposition, as market-oriented design may well respond to ethical, social or environmental needs (Dewberry, 2000; Margolin and Margolin 2002; Moreli, 2007). Thus more market-oriented concept has won broad appeal such as 'green consumerism' and 'ethical investment'. Also the prevalence of sustainability issues in consumer publication stimulates the purchase of socially responsible products and services. However, only a few electronics companies, such as Philips, Electrolux, IBM, and Xerox, in the early 1990s began to

promote 'green design' or 'eco-design', which only considers environmental impacts. There still has been a lack of opportunity for the holistic approaches encompassing social and environmental concerns in the commercial design industries. This shortcoming is derived from designers' lack of awareness of many CSR-related issues, and also from organisations' lack of understanding about the crucial role of design in actually implementing and operationalising CSR.

Recently, a great deal of research has articulated how to identify the area where a social dimension can be added to the basic business domains, linking business ethics with competitive advantage as well as a critical strategy concept (Kakabadse et al., 2005; Porter and Kramer, 2006; Heslin and Ochoa, 2008; Carroll and Buchholtz, 2008). However, much of this research has been conducted solely from the management perspective, rather than from the design perspective, as an integral part of realization of the principles of CSR; therefore, to a certain extent, a gap still exists between CSR strategies and tactics and their realistic implementation and performance achieved by design. Thus far, there has arguably been more limited research debate about the role of design in CSR-related decision-making and the impact of these elements on corporate social performance. Furthermore, little research has been done on the effect of design management capacity on translating the principles of CSR into manufactured goods as well as potential services (Hands, 2009). Whilst, in recent management literature many researchers began to pay attention to the perceptions of managers toward CSR and their real action they may take regarding socially responsible issues (Jamali and Sidani, 2008; Quazi and O'Brien 2000). This is because managers not only make decisions that reflect their assessment of the role of the company, but also make judgment as to whether there will be net benefits or net costs to the company associated with the CSR action. In a related vein, it can be argued that designer's perception and behavioural attitude regarding corporate social responsibility and socially responsible design issues are also a crucial part of organisational decision making notably in new product and service development, and further have a great impact on the firm's economic, environmental, and social performance. Therefore the objective of this study is to empirically investigate how designers

perceive CSR in the context of South Korea companies and what motivates these designers to develop socially responsible products and services, with special reference to the electronics industry. This article aims to address the primary research questions: (i) what is the designers' awareness and knowledge of corporate social responsibility?; and (ii) What is the designers' underlying motivation for socially responsible design decision-making?

2. THE TWO-DIMENSIONAL MODEL OF SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE DESIGN (SRD) DECISION MAKING

Keeping in mind the increasing importance of individual members' perception and behavioural attitude in actually operationalising CSR, a two-dimensional model of socially responsible design decision-making is proposed. The model is depicted in Figure 1. To empirically assess the current status of CSR from design perspectives, the model has two axes representing (i) *attitudes and actual behaviour of individual designers* and (ii) *corporate regulation* affecting their behavioural attitudes within the organisational context. The horizontal axis of the framework has two extremes: *regulation* and *non-regulation* regarding socially responsible design at the company level. The right hand extreme represent *company-regulated* (i.e. it is part of company's processes, regulation, and policy) SRD decision-making where the designers' responsibility toward customers, local community, and natural environments is perceived in the legitimate sense. By contrast, the left extreme represents *non-regulated* view of SRD actions where the organisation does not regulate for any aspects of CSR. The only socially responsible design that would take place is very limited through a designer's personal ethical value system. The vertical axis of the model represents two extremes in designers' awareness of the need to develop SRD at individual level, ranging from making a fully *conscious* design decision in terms of social and environmental issues to making an *unconscious* design decision without being aware of the importance of SRD. Thus the model proposed has four distinct quadrants. Each quadrant is named as follows:

Quadrant A. Company-regulated, conscious design decision-making: This quadrant represents a *company and designer-led* approach. In this quadrant, both

organisations and individual designers are *consciously* aware of CSR decision-making and they engage in *formalised* discussions about CSR. Businesses adopt some degree of voluntary regulatory standards as a part of their genuine commitment to social responsibility, as they believe those actions will lead to net benefit to the company in terms, for example, of avoiding costly and embarrassing regulation, building good customer relationships, good supplier relationships or the politics of networking.

Quadrant B. Non-regulated, but conscious design decision-making: This is concerned with a socially conscious *designer-led* approach toward SRD in which there is no company regulation related to SRD as top/middle management sees it as a cost-generating factor to the company without any real benefit flowing from an activity. Yet individual designers make decisions in socially conscious ways based on their personal ethical value system, reaching beyond a narrow view of company regulation.

Quadrant C. Non-regulated, unconscious design decision-making: This view captures a perspective in which a business has no provision to look beyond a narrow view of profit maximisation. From this perspective, any part of socially responsible design decision making is unconscious and non-regulated; rather it can often be seen as a response from the

market which is actually a *society-led* approach.

Quadrant D. Company-regulated, but unconscious design decision-making: This quadrant depicts designers' *informal/unconscious* CSR decision-making. In this quadrant, corporations tend to follow existing guidelines and regulations to fulfil minimum CSR criteria, but designers are not formally conscious of CSR and develop products and services only in a manner that adheres to the company's legal and economic responsibilities; this has nothing to do with a formal commitment to social responsibility, but rather a business strategy to reduce cost, or to secure regulatory compliance within the focus of its economic value.

3. DESIGNER INTERVIEW ANALYSIS

For the empirical research, 31 designers involved in the two multinational electronics companies (see Appendix 1). For the purpose of the investigation, the electronics sector in South Korea has been identified as the industrial limiting factor with three important theoretical considerations. This has been determined because (i) technology is advancing very quickly, and therefore many products are short-lived, causing a huge e-waste problem, (ii) there is a transportation issue of electronic products made from Korea and China, which is also a huge environmental issue associated to CSR, and (iii) the environmental and social issues are more

Figure 1. A two dimensional model of SRD decision-making

associated in the electronic industry, which is directly related to CSR. In-depth interviews with ranges of designers in the two multinational companies were conducted to identify an individual's attitudes and perceptions of CSR-related issues and its influence on the perceived performance of socially responsible design (SRD). The following result is based on the themes identified through the analysis of the interviews and the examples provided by the 31 designers.

4. MAIN RESULTS

4-1. AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF CSR-RELATED ISSUES

There was a consensus amongst all interviewees that CSR is becoming increasingly prevalent within the industry. However, when directly asked about CSR, most designers were not familiar with the concept; less than 10% of those interviewed viewed CSR as integrating the concerns for the welfare of society with the management processes of the firm from a strategic standpoint. Almost all of the interviewees discussed several areas including monetary donations, community involvement, environmental prevention, strengthening customer satisfaction, creating jobs, promoting win-win partnership with small and mid-sized companies and/or business ethics. This is encouraging as all of the issues mentioned are congruent with a current focal shift of CSR moving beyond philosophical consideration of social and moral concerns toward specific issues-oriented approach to better respond to external environment such as political and social situations.

With respect to the most common matters mentioned, almost 53% of respondents viewed CSR as something that would respond to environmental concerns such as minimising the impact on the environment through recycling, decreasing energy consumption, or acquiring eco-design qualification. Another key figure showed that 47% of interviewees viewed CSR as companies' community involvement through charitable contributions, investment in educational programs, art and culture, or employees' volunteer projects. For example, several interviewees mentioned that corporate giving failed to make a connection with their job role as a designer. This suggests knowledge of these areas without engaging operating design management in identifying value chain impacts and social dimensions of the competitive

context. This awareness of concerns without understanding their full thoughts is important, understanding the issues without understating its strategic implication or its importance relative to designing process makes it difficult to make a far greater positive impact on societal issues as well as a long-term business benefit. Attempting to design products and services on the basis of treating CSR as merely charitable giving or corporate image without understanding how either CSR interacts with operating design management or how strategic CSR positioning creates a unique and sustainable competitive position, may result in a fragmented, defensive stance of CSR. In addition, 18% of respondents thought that CSR embraced the ideas of fair business practices such as anti-corruption, including extortion and bribery. For instance, interviewee 30 saw CSR as eradicating illegalities and corruption, which have contributed to serious problems caused by the plutocracy in South Korea, whilst, interviewee 17 regarded CSR as a way of maintaining a win-win relationship with smaller enterprises. This opinion seemed to be pervaded by company policy aligned with government regulation that was specifically amended for the cooperative relationship in 2010. In addition to the above points, 12% of those interviewed mentioned enhancing consumer satisfaction through offering high quality after-sale service and communication as a key factor of CSR. Less than 10% of the respondents discussed the economic development of the community. For instance, interviewee 12 suggested the significance of the company invigorating local employment economy through creation of wealth and increased employment.

4-2. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CSR AND DESIGN

When directly questioned about the perception of their roles in delivering CSR, some designers failed to make a direct link between their job role and CSR, but most designers questioned perceived that there was both a direct and indirect relationship between the two. Many interviewees recognised that the design role fulfils responsibility in terms of profitable businesses, quality of life for people, and the environment. This illustrates the interviewee's views on the significance of the economic, environmental and social variables in creating a successful yet responsible development process. Recognising the relationship between the three

dimensions and design is important. However, throughout the interviews, it also was found that most design issues related to environmental or social dimensions are closely associated with the firm's economic responsibility. This reflects that economic responsibility is the underpinning of both social and environmental responsibilities, at least in a South Korean context, and thus it is difficult to separate economic responsibility from environment or social ones. This is not only because of the interconnected nature of the economy, society and the environment, but also because of the high possibility of motivation for socially responsible activities being different from the firm's genuine purpose. Therefore, the following sections build upon the discussion of specific design issues during new product and service development within environmental and societal dimensions, where opportunities to create real economic value reside. The research findings from interviews of designers identified a list of topics in respect of environmental and social aspects of design (Figure 2). Those topics will be discussed in detail in the next sections.

1) Environmental Dimension

28 of the 31 interviews discussed the environmental focus within socially-responsible design. The most popular response was to develop eco-friendly products. Throughout the interviews, there appeared to be a strong emphasis on the environmental factor being the most significant part of contribution design can make to support a delivery of CSR. Interviewee 9 suggested that this focus on the environmental aspect was because it was the most visible way in taking action as well as appealing their socially responsible business practice against ever tightening environmental regulation, particularly in the case of the manufacturing industry.

(i) Manufacture stage

Most issues raised by product designers focus on the choice of materials, and manufacturing processes. Almost all industrial designers interviewed primarily considered their roles as mitigating the environmental impact of products in the production stage, more specifically through (i) reducing the number of components, materials, and type of materials, (ii) removing toxic materials contained in products, (iii) use of renewable or recycled materials, (iv) use of process that require less manufacturing energy and materials,

and/or (v) minimised use of mock-up. These were supported by the use of examples such as PVC-free materials, reusable/disposable plastic and aluminium, and more environmentally friendly manufacturing methods, such as non-laminated coating method or reducing use of paint.

First, interviewees 5, 11, 13, 16, and 17 suggested that the most common approach to ecological design is to reduce the number of manufacturing processes, especially for post-processing, by eliminating fancy elements in pursuit of simplicity in form, whilst reducing production costs.

Secondly, the issue of removing toxic materials contained in products was discussed by interviewee 10 as a response to the regulatory pressure. Interviewee 12 also suggested that ecological initiatives, especially for hazardous substance management, are actually driven by environmental regulation as external regulatory stakeholders and this, in turn, directs designers or engineers to adopt more environmentally responsible design actions. Therefore, this aspect arguably represents company regulation-led approaches, but unconscious decision-making of designers, because although designers are not fully aware that all environmentally harmful materials need to be excluded during the design processes, company guidelines strictly prohibit them from using materials containing toxic substances which are banned by global regulation, such as Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS), to sell their products in global markets like the EU.

Thirdly, the issue of using renewable or recycled materials in the physical appearance of products was discussed by interviewee 5, with the example of an eco-friendly mobile phone. The solar-powered, eco-friendly phone is made of recycled water bottles and packed in a reusable box made of recycled paper without using bleach, adhesives or coatings in order to be effectively recycled. According to interviewee 5, this was driven by management with the aim of exhibiting and testing its advanced environmental technologies to the market, whilst responding proactively to changes in future environmental regulation. With this company-led approach to environmental responsibility, designers were encouraged to display green thinking, and it required a close collaboration with engineering functions, as much of the tangible improvement in terms of environmental performance comes from the engineering side. This suggests the existence and

availability of technology or materials (e.g. use of a recycled plastic from water bottles called PCM) was a critical factor in driving forward environmental sustainability, especially in terms of material concerns.

Fourthly, the issue of module communisation is an example that was motivated strictly by economic imperatives, yet has had a positive impact on the environment as an unintended consequence.

Interviewees 10 and 13 discussed module communisation in terms of standardising components so they can be used in many different models, increasing the lifespan of the subsystem even when the software, casing or other components change over time.

Interviewee 10 admitted, although this stemmed from a tangible economic benefit by gaining economies of scale, this would, in turn, lead to a reduction in environmental impact with an optimised manufacturing process and reduced use of resources by designing components to be interchangeably used and replaced within the same product category quickly and cost-effectively. However, interviewee 10's statement *'these are things that the designer does not recognise but they are actually working for the environment'*, seems to suggest that the respondent did not necessarily intend to decrease the environmental impact of the products, but rather, she focused on improving efficiency in the use of natural resources as a definitive responsibility to the company. This suggests that module communisation issues are often regulated by company guidelines due to its economic value, rather than initially motivated by conscious design decision-making toward environmental responsibility as a designer.

Finally, interviewee 13 identified the possibility of reducing prototypes in the design development process with the use of virtual reality technology. He also discussed this ecological initiative during a physical development process as an opportunity for self-reflection to drive change in top management styles. This would cause the business to question the necessity and validity of retaining hundreds of product models and making thousands of prototypes even within the mobile communication sector. A further point raised by interviewee 4 identified the need for improving value within their business, driving down environmental costs and improving efficiency by reducing the consumption of resources with an optimised number of product line-ups, not just in terms of a product itself, but also on an

entire business level. This suggests that the firm's environmental impact needs to be considered in terms of business effectiveness; that is, in terms of the ratio between the natural resources and energy required for the development of new products and services and their economic effects. The impact of work efficiency, especially in the manufacturing industry, is also important when considering long term environmental issues. Enhancing business efficiency by strategic product planning may have unforeseen positive consequences on the implementation of initiatives and the general development of CSR.

(ii) Distribution stage

The recent progress from heavy to smaller or lighter packaging design was discussed by interviewee 29, who stated that it was unintended and a natural consequence (or requirement) as products became smaller with the evolution of technology and/or changes in consumer needs. Interviewee 28 suggested that since packaging feature design and logistics costs are closely linked, there were also examples of economic value driven by the company to determine the most cost-efficient size for product packaging. In particular, interviewee 16 provided a business case for a washing machine packaging redesign project. The purpose was to replace the packaging that covers the whole surface with paper with an eco-friendly package designed to use paper only for the top and the bottom, to insert the paper container structure that enhances the paper, and to use eco-friendly vinyl material to wrap around the washing machine. According to interviewee 16, this had the effect of planting nearly 200,000 trees yearly. Therefore, it can be recognised as a significant environmental improvement through ecological redesign by eliminating unnecessary parts of packaging and by using recyclable material. In his statement *'[...] the starting point of this ecological approach didn't begin with the intension of protecting the environment in an environmentally friendly manner but began with the intention of reducing the packaging logistics cost, but it has brought these effect. [...]*', it is suggested that businesses are intrinsically concerned with economic return, and the environmentally friendly design approach originated from benefits for the business in a socio-economic sense coupled with the designers' conscious awareness of the need to develop environmentally sustainable products and services.

Nevertheless, there is a dilemma between many aspects of packaging design and environmental responsibility, as discussed by interviewees 28 and 29. Since packaging not only protects the product but also is a tool of exhibition, it is widely acknowledged in retail shops that the package carries a message from the producer to the consumer about the product. The message, apart from being informative, also has an advertising effect, which is crucial in the present market situation. In this context, interviewees 28 suggested that packaging as an advertising medium has (almost) the highest preference both inside (the design, sales and marketing teams) and outside (the local liaisons) of the company. However, interviewee 28 went on to claim that the current role of packaging was misled as the result of excessive competition for achieving a higher market share by catching the eye of consumers with the use of more luxurious and colourful package features, such as the use of full-colour printing or gold foil print. A company's view of using packaging mainly as a tool of seduction management to lure consumers requires more use of post-processing, which, of course, consumes more electronics, releasing more Co2 and discharging waste water. This is indeed in opposition to the green thinking. It is therefore important to recognise the urgent need for designers to achieve balance of the interdependencies not only between packaging feature design and advertisement, but also between packaging design and its environmental impact, from manufacturing to distribution and to final disposal.

(iii) Use stage

Generally, the interviewees believed that there is a stronger connection between giving products a physical shape and designers' environmental responsibility; this is because the role of product designers directly relates to using physical resources. Whilst, the general consensus was that user experience (UX) and user interface (UI) designer chiefly regarded their role as designing interfaces and system with future needs in mind where possible, and creating a user experience that can potentially lead to the users' behavioural change toward a more environmentally sustainable lifestyle.

Interviewee 25 viewed their role in relation to environmental sustainability, as designing platforms that are able to be upgraded. This illustrates the key

role of UX and UI designers in extending product life-cycle and maintaining its highest value. This highlights the idea of designers thinking about the whole life cycle of products which are durable goods that provide a service to customers especially in the electronics industry (McDonough and Braungart, 2002). As discussed during many interviews, upgrades are not easy with lots of technological products, even though they are even more appropriate since the evolution of technological change is so rapid. Interviewee 25 goes on to give an example of what is happening in the company and why it is difficult to achieve upgrades; there are two factors affecting this: management's narrow mindset and the focus on short term economic gains. Interviewee 25's statement, *'That is not easy technically and rather than the voice of the designer, the voice of the executives who have the thought of "new products must look new" and the pressure to sell new products is bigger, so these ideas are not well accepted. Version up is not something all people think of throughout the company. However, within the limits of what I can do, I believe the responsibility for the environment is important'*, suggested there was no company regulation or willingness on the part of management related to upgradability since the executives did not want to be responsible for the risk of uncertainty, and they thought it to be more economically sustainable to sell as many products as possible, extracting the most profits from them for the short-term, at least during the tenure of the executive, typically a one-year contract.

On the other hand, there were cases driven by company recognition of the need to develop a more advanced level of eco-product by incorporating the ecological concept with the product's UI and UX aspects. For example, interviewee 22 perceived his role as creating an eco-friendly user experience that can potentially lead to users' behavioural change toward a more environmentally friendly way of living. During the interview, the respondent identified that there was a change in the view of 'eco design' from applying it with hardware issues to internalising it with intangible aspects of design. A more colourful and succinct description was given by interviewee 22, as follows:

"there was the Eco-walk app designed to tell the user how much CO2 emission he/she saved by walking instead of driving, and depending on which trees in the idle screen design grew, reflecting how they reduced their environmental impact. [...] Another UX design

feature used for the eco-phone was the Eco-unlock, which has a refuse bin and can on the unlock screen. Whenever the user drags and drops the can in the refuse bin with recycling icons, then it unlocks the phone, and when the phone unlocks, the screen provides users with information of how much they can contribute to the environment if they recycles a certain number of cans. It gives meaning to the refresh action itself. Through doing this behaviour, the user is able to feel indirectly how much he or she is helping protect the environment. That was something the person didn't know before, but the person will begin to think these actions will be greatly helpful for the environment and will have more interest in this area and think more about this than before."

In addition, many interviewees discussed the concept of saving energy, although there was distinct uncertainty regarding how designers could contribute to improving energy efficiency. An example of a companywide energy-saving initiative using a GUI design solution was addressed by interviewee 23: *'For example, in the case of ultra-low energy TV, manual features like the power-saving features are approached through the technological part, but the aspect the design part can propose is the screen colour. It was inspired by knowing the fact that energy use is significantly different in black and white. White or bright colours are tones that consume more energy, and black or dark colours consume less energy, in using electricity, there is a big difference between the two. I proposed a concept that it is better in design as well as in energy saving if you make the menu screen darker'*. It is evident that the importance of a company's energy-saving initiatives relates directly to potential benefit not only to the environment but also to the users and the company as well. In other words, those company actions usually originate from market trends reflecting needs of consumers who want to save more money on electricity, yet this would eventually result in reduced CO2 emissions and thus creates a sort of vicious circle.

2) Social Dimension

The social dimension relates to people and communities; it focuses on how designers deal, within their daily design practices, with the aspects of human rights, consumers, and social and economic development of the community which are the key constituents of CSR. The elusive notion of CSR, the

vagueness around the term and the lack of education about what it means to be socially reasonable were all cited from designers' perspectives as reasons why people focus primarily on just considering the environment when talking about CSR. As such, the social dimension is often the least discussed responsibility, especially at the project level, and this was illustrated in the interviews, as most interviewees had to be prompted to talk about the social aspect of their business. The interviewees discussed two distinct perspectives in relation to the social aspect: (i) social contribution through donating design talent or cause-related marketing, and (ii) developing socially responsible products and services.

(i) Social contribution through donating design talent or cause-related marketing

When directly asked about a perceived relationship between CSR and design, many interviewees appeared to fail to link social aspect of CSR with their daily design activities. Apart from the actual design development process, interviewees discussed employee voluntary programs by donating design talent (e.g. design education of the younger generation, voluntary work for mural painting, etc.). Some interviewees suggested a possible connection between CSR and design, referring to marketing campaign-led approaches to CSR. For example, there was a discussion by interviewee 16 about the merits of selling products with a good cause through CSR-informed communication strategy. This approach is known as cause-related marketing and includes marketing initiatives based on the cooperative efforts of business 'for profit' and charitable causes. They believed this had a more direct economic benefit for a deprived local community than any other design involvement. However, in a real practise situation, the interviewee admitted there are many difficulties in adopting those cooperative efforts within the current organisational culture as the company still focuses on short-term profit-making strategies, even if embracing a cause would make good business sense in the long term.

(ii) Developing socially responsible products and services

When indirectly questioned about the broader role of design in addressing social aspect of CSR, several issues were considered broadly by the interviewees, yet

without articulating them as to being ‘socially responsible’ design practices. However, when actually analysing their design approach, it appeared that many interviewees partly make decisions, potentially realising their social responsibility through both tangible and intangible design solutions.

Throughout the interviews, there was a discussion about a broad concept of enhancing the quality of people’s lives. Since understanding and responding to customers has become a key element in expressing social responsibility, relevant design issues have been considered in a user-oriented manner. From industrial designers’ perspectives, the commitment to building a happier and more convenient world to live in was identified as one of the fundamental and inherent responsibilities toward people and the community. For example, interviewees 9 and 12 recognised the fact that the primary role of designers is to create better products that are essential for people’s lives, by which designers are naturally yet unconsciously fulfilling their responsibility both for the company and the society they belong to. Whilst creating products and services based upon designers’ job responsibilities may be beneficial, initially, in gaining imminent economic gains, it is not sufficient to address a holistic dimension of social responsibility. This is because it is basically tied up with serving the economic interests of the firm to run its business in a financially sustainable manner, rather than motivated by an adherence to its human/societal values. In this vein, many product designers viewed designers’ social responsibility not just as creating best-selling products, but more importantly designing for people’s needs and desires. Interviewee 17 considered that creating innovative products based on human aspirations and lifestyle before people even knew they wanted it could be a process of implementing designers’ social responsibility. However, this discussion was, to a certain degree, limited to the aspect of giving products attractive appearances in a traditional view of design. From UI designers’ perspectives, interviewee 23 made a more philosophical connection to the role of designers in satisfying the meaning and value needs of people. With the increasing importance of providing a variety of information through intangible service, attempting to design a service system without understanding the context of its use or how the information/content will influence people’s quality of life may result in an

ineffective and unnecessarily complex design solution, which might not be socially responsible. This is an important point trying to move toward human-centred approach by reflecting the social responsibility of designers, whilst balancing the aim of the business and people’s desires and needs.

In terms of product liability, there was strong feeling that protecting consumers’ health and safety is central to addressing CSR. As such, interviewees 3, 11, 12, and 13 suggested it is crucial for them to pay attention to product liability and to carefully look at whether there are any parts that could harm customers; yet, it appeared to be one of the primary job responsibilities directed by company regulation to comply with Product Liability (PL) law, ensuring the company has the right to sell its products to the market.

There was a discussion about affordability in terms of allowing people living in poverty to make their social lives a little more abundant with mobile products. Interviewee 1 believed that by designing a mobile phone that only contains essential and fundamental functions and offering it at an affordable price they are indirectly contributing to enhancing people’s quality of life in the local community. However, interviewee 27 claimed that they did not create a phone for people in underdeveloped regions with the intention of improving their standard of living; rather, the interviewee suggested that the product with essential features only was developed with the aim of enhancing the company’s entry-level market share and cost competitiveness. The results can be the same, but the approaching mindsets are different.

On the other hand, a possible connection between design and CSR was made by the discussion about design for accessibility and inclusivity. Interviewees 9, 10, and 21 saw inclusive design features as socially responsible design action. For example, interviewee 10 stated that IT products, such as note-PCs and printers that are designed to be used universally, can guarantee equal opportunities among different social groups, such as people with disabilities. In this sense, interviewee 10 regarded the inclusive design feature as a positive example of implicitly incorporating social responsibility with products whilst serving the firm’s economic cause. However, interviewee 5 discussed the difficulties faced by designers in developing a ‘design for all’. He thought it was almost impossible to develop a product covering minority groups, such as people with disabilities, due to

its limited marketability. This approach lacks a holistic understanding of what inclusivity really means; that is about extending user groups to take into account the needs of older persons and persons with disabilities, and does not necessarily mean developing products for those people only, to the exclusion of normal users.

The discussion with UI and UX designers about social dimension of responsibility tended to focus mainly on usability issues. For example, GUI (graphic user interface) designers especially recognised the importance of usability of mobile phones for the elderly. According to interviewee 21, she developed a new guideline for the button and font sizes that focuses on enhanced usability, notably for the elderly, reconciling the necessary information on the button and font size with visual appeal and attractiveness for general mobile phone users. Although the interviewee 2 did not think she considered CSR during her design process, she actually internalised the CSR principle regarding caring for vulnerable groups through a user-centered design approach, creating a new physical interface of the mobile phone for all.

The social aspect seemed to be more implicitly involved with the user-centred design process, and it was often accompanied though non-regulated and unconscious design decision-making processes. As such, many interviewees were making design decisions without articulating it as ‘socially responsible’ design

actions. During the interviews, there was a lot of focus on the effect of design upon people and society, but one significant element did recur throughout the interviews, which was the lack of a definitive definition of what it is to be socially responsible from design perspectives, and the high possibility that motivation for socially responsible activities are different from their genuine purpose. In this sense, interviewee 15, 18, and 21 pointed out that those unconscious decisions toward SRD often originate from the firm’s economic cause to satisfy unmet needs of the current and potential customer. As such, the respondents admitted those design decision are not genuinely derived from a sense of social responsibility, but rather from their job responsibility.

5. CONCLUSION

Many interviewees discussed the dominance of the economic perspective that underscores the practice of SRD. So, ironically, although our interviewees acknowledged the importance of social and environmental dimensions, the prevalence of the economic viewpoint of the corporations means that genuine consideration for community and the environment remains largely elusive. However, there was also recognition amongst 70% of the interviewees that there can be a difference in the products and

Figure 2. The dynamic two dimensional model of SRD decision-making

services designed by a designer who is aware of social and environmental issues and a designer who is not, regardless of the existence of a company's regulation in terms of corporate social responsibility.

Firstly, our exploratory review revealed that conscious decisions really have to do with regulations of the company. This is evident that 15 out of 21 items have a close connection with the company's legislated requirements (see Figure 2). Notably, 12 items made in the quadrant "A" were directly or indirectly involved with a *formalised* discussion about CSR within the organisation. The interesting aspect here is that many of those decisions did not initially originate from the quadrant "A" but from "D"(see transition stage "a") That is, at the beginning, the majority of design decisions related to the social and environmental dimensions appeared as unintentional consequences that come from the firm's pursuit of economic gains and/or the firm's desire to avoid costly and embarrassing regulation. As such, in the quadrant "D", designers often automatically fulfil their job roles because the business strategy means a philosophy designers need to take on board when they make design decisions without any moral and ethical validation or judgments of right and wrong, as parts of their unconscious activities. In this organisational context, it is argued that many designers are making economically and regally conscious decisions within a boundary of company guidelines, yet that are formally *unconscious* in terms of CSR. However, the transition stage "a" means that once designers identified the fact that those actions will lead to net benefit to society as well as business, both the company and designers become conscious about CSR and then socially responsible design processes could be a part of the system within the organisation.

Secondly, it was also identified that designers do make other *conscious* decisions based on their own ethics and value systems that were not necessarily codified into the company regulation and guidelines, as well as have not yet been clearly articulated within an organisation. This means that the organisation is unaware of what designers make conscious decisions on and designers cannot tell the organisation about that. For this reason, many socially conscious design issues belonging to the quadrant "B" frequently fail to proceed into the next higher level of decision-making by the marketing or top management. Many

interviewees suggested the main conflict in incorporating CSR thinking within the new product development process was in relation to either the additional costs involved or the perceived additional costs involved with 'socially responsible' projects. Interviewees noted that they were working within a restricted budget allocated by the product planning team and had to be careful when using environmentally friendly materials, which are normally more expensive. In the private sector, if a project's business case cannot return the required margin, it will not go ahead; it becomes economically irresponsible for the shareholders. However, the findings from the interviews suggested there were also driving forces, in a variety of guises, from reputation management, investment in future technologies, and to a proactive response to the potential regulatory risks. With the underlying motivations, some environmental issues were moved from the quadrant "B" to "A" (see transition stage "b") only after designers have clearly articulated its socio-economic benefits in relation to CSR as well as the potential business opportunities, and the top management have a strong willingness to operationalise and implement CSR through the design of socially responsible products and services.

Another level of decisions designers make is unconscious decisions during their design processes based on just their own insights and knowledge that have not really consciously explained and could be seen as a response to a market or media (the quadrant "C"). For example, the company's energy saving initiative (no.13) primarily emerged to effectively respond to the fast-changing market conditions and to reflect changed attitudes in our society. However, it has now become a formalised design process for smart TVs within the company, after designers and marketers consciously recognise the intangible role of design in contributing to the reduction in energy use through a careful choice of display colours (see transition stage "c"). Understanding trade-offs in socially responsible design decision-making is therefore critical and it need to be conscious trade-offs, rather than unconscious trade-offs.

Finally, it was suggested that CSR issues are partly and potentially valid in designers' daily decisions, even though the designers may not clearly articulate it. This arguably express the idea of conscious decision-making driven by designers' own ethics and value system that has not become regulated or standardised within the

organisation. However, CSR and socially responsible design can cause something to become regulated. Once the socially conscious design practices are recognised within an organisation, they have something more of regulatory status and become imbedded in the process; and then, socially responsible design will eventually become a part of formal process for hundreds of new product deployment projects going on within the company. It is therefore argued that if they could articulate what they are doing in terms of social responsibility, the impact would be greater on truly and genuine conscious decision-making toward SRD. Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed two dimensional model of SRD decision-making has been empirically supported by the emergence of the three possible transition stages, further suggesting a possibility of a more dynamic model to operate.

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